

D4.5 - Business Model and Sustainability Study

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Deliverable Abstract
<p>This deliverable documents the results of EOSC-Pillar Task 4.5 activity. It summarises its findings regarding sustainable business models collected through surveys, interviews and workshops involving EOSC stakeholders in Austria, Belgium, France, Germany and Italy.</p> <p>The picture emerging from these exchanges at EOSC-Pillar scale is a complex and fragmented landscape where there is no single answer to the question of the preferred Business Model for national Open Science initiatives, thematic research infrastructures and service providers. Our conclusions have to be put in perspective in the quickly evolving context at national and international levels with all the uncertainties related to the outcome of the EOSC procurement tenders by the European Commission and the evolution of the energy price.</p> <p>The priority is not to freeze a business model for EOSC but rather continue exploring all avenues to keep the services free at the point of use.</p>

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TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

<i>Terminology/Acronym</i>	<i>Definition</i>
BM	Business Model
TF	Task Force
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package of the EOSC-Pillar project

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Executive summary

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) is a complex multi-stakeholder environment including national research infrastructures, thematic research infrastructures and various stakeholders. EOSC-Pillar is one of the regional projects funded by the INFRA EOSC topic to provide inputs to build EOSC. Relying on regional interactions, EOSC-Pillar includes France, Italy, Germany, Belgium, and Austria and could be considered as a “mini-EOSC” where issues and possible solutions can be identified with a smaller number of stakeholders.

The present document describes the work done by task 4.5 during the course of the project and summarises its findings regarding sustainable business models in the context of our “mini-EOSC” that could be extended to EOSC.

Results were collected through three main modalities of action:

1. Desk research to collect existing works on business models and sustainability proposed by the different projects and Working Groups.
2. Surveys and interviews with the different stakeholders identified as relevant in the project both at National level and at individual service provider/scientific communities level to identify how business models are handled at the different scales.
3. Organisation of workshops with international stakeholders to collect inputs and recommendations on business models.

In the five countries involved in EOSC-Pillar (Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, Italy), as in many extra-EU countries such as Australia, Canada, South Africa and even China, public funding is the main source of revenue for developing and operating services for Open Science. One of the main identified obstacles for service providers to develop business models is the lack of an agreed methodology to compute unit costs. A clear recommendation is the need to develop a clear cost model to build trust with funders and users.

An emerging concern expressed by the organisations interviewed is the environmental impact of digital technologies. The current international political and economic instability induced by the war in Ukraine adds major uncertainties on the energy supply in Europe that impacts the running costs for computing and storage resource providers. The construction of EOSC must take into account the need for optimising the energetic cost of the services to be offered all along the data life cycle both for environmental and economic concerns.

Our exploration of Business Models for services coming out of scientific communities involved in EOSC-Pillar allowed us to identify several potential patterns for Open Science IT Services. A unique model is not foreseeable as legal frameworks are different in each European country and scientific communities have different cultures/practices. Exploration of Innovative approaches should be encouraged like for instance numerical commons.

Representatives of international research communities shared their views and thoughts on business models during the workshops co-organized by EOSC-Pillar. They stressed the importance of keeping the European and the national levels aligned, in order to ensure the connection between the

A faint, light-colored map of Europe serves as the background for the page. The map shows the outlines of the continents and major countries, with a slightly darker shade of blue for the landmasses and a lighter shade for the surrounding waters.

European interest and national strategies. Transnational service access also requires an European level organisation due to the complexity of the transactions. Recommendations stemming from the workshops include increasing the uptake of implementation and fulfilment of FAIR principles, harmonising policies, licensing and procedures for storing and accessing data and resources at national and international level in order to build a sustainable model to fund access.

The workshops were also the opportunity to witness the emergence of National initiatives that could take over a coordinating role in the governance of Open Science development at the national level. The e-infrastructures also play an essential role in the provision of EOSC Core services. Their revenue coming from the European Commission is at risk as the procurement tender launched in December 2022 by the European Commission for EOSC services may result in a migration of service provision from e-Infrastructure to private companies.

Our final recommendation is therefore to continue exploring the different BM avenues to keep the services free at the point of use and to integrate the energy cost optimization for a successful environmental transition.

1 Introduction

1.1 Context of this work

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) was identified by the European Commission as a major element to foster innovation in the Digital Single Market Strategy¹. EOSC should provide a multidisciplinary environment for researchers to publish, find and re-use scientific data, tools and services. The role of EOSC has been investigated by various expert groups starting in 2016 with the “Realising the European open science cloud” report [1] which led to the EOSC Declaration setting the scene for EOSC² in 2017. Since then, the development of EOSC has been supported by a specific topic in the Horizon 2020 Work Program (INFRA-EOSC) funding several EU projects such as EOSC-Hub, EOSC Pilot, EOSC Secretariat which laid the foundation for the EOSC Association created in July 2020. The Association has been started by four members and has now grown to up to 200 members. The aim of the association is to develop a “web of FAIR data and services” for scientists across Europe.

By definition, EOSC is a complex multi-stakeholder environment including national research infrastructures, thematic research infrastructures and various stakeholders such as the research ministries from the different Member States. Due to the large diversity of legal, organisational and technical implementations across the Member States, it is practically impossible to converge on a simple solution to build a pan-European data infrastructure without investigating the context within each Member State and the existing and potential interactions between Member States. For this purpose, the H2020 Work program opened a call for (“thematic” and) “regional” proposals which should federate (research communities and) countries from specific regions (Nordic, Balkans, Mediterranean, Western Europe).

EOSC-Pillar is one of these regional projects funded by the INFRA EOSC topic to provide inputs to build EOSC. Relying on regional interactions, EOSC-Pillar includes France, Italy, Germany, Belgium, and Austria. In a sense, EOSC-Pillar is supposed to be considered as a “mini-EOSC” to identify the issues and possible solutions with a smaller number of stakeholders. The aggregation of these inputs has been done through a tight collaboration between the regional projects (EOSC Nordic, EOSC Synergy, Ni4OS). The strength of EOSC-Pillar relies on the diversity of the stakeholders involved and in particular the strong link with National Initiatives and the extensive participation of scientific communities and service providers supported by the 9 use-cases driving the project (WP6) and the “ready-to-use” services proposed by infrastructure providers (WP7). The number of use-cases and services has been extended during the course of the project through an Open Call launched in 2021.

Besides the necessity to build a technical and legal framework allowing transnational federation of IT resources, the key issue of EOSC is to address the following question: how to build a sustainable global infrastructure? As of now, this endeavour is supported by the European Commission funding,

¹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A52015DC0192>

² https://eosc-portal.eu/sites/default/files/eosc_declaration.pdf

through the creation of specific calls for proposals in the Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe Work Programs. Is this funding stream sustainable in the long term? What should be the contributions of the Member States? What would be an optimal business model for a sustainable EOSC?

EOSC-Pillar started in 2019, at the time of the EOSC Secretariat project which initiated different Working Groups to address specific issues around EOSC. In particular, a dedicated Working Group has been focusing on the sustainability of EOSC. The conclusions of this working group have been published in the “fair lady” report [2]. At the same period, other projects investigated the aspects of sustainability and business models for a sustainable EOSC e.g. EOSC-Hub, EOSC Pilot and EOSC-Pillar.

The present document aims at describing the work done by task 4.5 during the course of the project, taking into account the work done in the other projects and Working Groups and summarising our findings regarding sustainable business models in the context of our “mini-EOSC” that could be extended to EOSC.

1.2 Objectives of this work

The main objectives of the task are multi-fold. First, the task aims to propose different possible business models supporting trans-disciplinary data, computing and open science services and infrastructure at the national and transnational level in the context of EOSC-Pillar and beyond. To support this, the task also surveyed beacons of good practices from non-European countries (e.g. USA, Japan, Australia) and organised workshops gathering national stakeholders and relevant funding agencies, together with relevant international organisations and initiatives, including RDA and CODATA, to get their feedback and input during this process.

This document presents our attempt to address all these objectives in a rapidly evolving context.

1.3 Methodology

To achieve our objectives, we identified three main modalities of action:

1. Investigate the work on business models and sustainability proposed by the different projects and Working Groups. The result of this investigation is summarised in section 2 and was used as background information for this work.
2. Conduct interviews with the different stakeholders identified as relevant in the project both at National level and at individual service provider/scientific communities level to identify how business models are handled at the different scales.
3. Organise a workshop with international stakeholders to collect inputs and recommendations on business models.

To provide a common approach to define business models within the project, we leveraged the Business Model Canvas proposed by Osterwalder et al. in 2005 [3]. The canvas is a strategic management template providing an overview of the crucial processes, resources, and infrastructure necessary to be considered for the creation of sustainable business models. The Business Model Canvas is organised around 9 different segments ([3]; [4]): customer segments, value propositions,

channels, customer relationships, revenue streams, key resources, key activities, key partnerships, and cost structure. The segments can be grouped into 4 main categories:

- **Value proposition/Offer:** Outlines the collection of services offered to create value for the customer. According to Osterwalder [5], value refers to the aspect of a service that distinguishes it from its competitors like newness, cost reduction, risk reduction and performance.
- **Infrastructure:** refers to the necessary elements to provide the value proposition
 - Key activities: Refers to the activities performed to create or capture the value proposition
 - Key resources: Describes the infrastructure, skills, and intangibles needed
 - Partner network: Outlines the required stakeholders, partners, and suppliers
- **Customers:** refers to the stakeholders for which the value proposition is tailored and how the service provider relates with the customers
 - Customer segment: Clarifies the different target customers to be addressed
 - Channels: Specifies which communication, distribution, and sales channels are used
 - Customer relationship: Describes how customers are acquired and retained by the value proposition
- **Finances** refers to the cost and revenue stream supporting the value proposition.
 - Cost structure: Highlights the costs incurred to generate the value
 - Revenue streams: Describes how the creation and capturing of the value is funded.

Figure 1. Template of the Business Model Canvas (Wikipedia).

Osterwalder and Pigneur [4] believe that a business model can best be described through nine basic building blocks that show the logic of how an organisation intends to make money (see Figure 1). “The nine blocks cover the four main areas of a business: customers, value proposition/offer, infrastructure, and financial viability. The business model is like a blueprint for a strategy to be implemented through organisational structures, processes, and systems. This tool resembles a painter’s canvas - pre-formatted with the nine blocks - which allows you to paint pictures of new or existing business models. The Business Model Canvas works best when printed out on a large surface so groups of people can jointly start sketching and discussing business model elements with sticky notes or board markers. It is a hands-on tool that fosters understanding, discussion, creativity, and analysis”.

The deliverable is organised as follows. In section 2, we are providing an overview of the various outcomes on sustainability proposed by the different projects: this overview provides the initial background information on business models and financial sustainability that has been considered in our investigations. In section 3, we present the results of EOSC-Pillar activities at both the national level and the individual communities/service provider level. In section 4, we highlight how the EOSC landscape has evolved during EOSC-Pillar lifetime and discuss briefly the conclusions of the EOSC Financial Sustainability Task Force Progress report published just at the end of EOSC-Pillar. Taking into account this rapidly evolving context, we then provide some conclusions and recommendations for a sustainable EOSC in section 5.

2 Background on business models

In this section, we will focus on the work done within the context of the EOSC Association and several EC Projects about EOSC business models. We will also explore the business models adopted by similar initiatives worldwide. We will adopt a chronological order starting with EOSC-Pilot (May 2019, [6]), followed by the EOSC Association FAIR lady report (November 2020, [2]) then EOSC-Hub WP12 deliverables (2020-2021,[7-9]). EOSC-Pillar activities conducted in parallel to these efforts are described in the next section.

Very recently (November 2022) the EOSC Association Financial Sustainability Task Force published its progress report [10]. Its recommendations are discussed together with EOSC-Pillar results in the conclusion of this document.

2.1 EOSC-Pilot

EOSC-Pilot identified that the main governance challenge of establishing the EOSC was to construct a framework allowing strong and disparate stakeholders to work together. EOSC-Pilot Work Package 3 produced a roadmap of practical policy actions to gradually establish the policy environment required for the effective operation of an Ethical, Open, Secure and Cost-effective EOSC [6]. Its recommendations can be summarised as follows:

- **Ethics:** Commit to a policy of maximal transparency and accountability, in the context of any activity that relates to EOSC data, data providers, services or users, including activities carried out with third parties.
- **Access:** EOSC resources must provide access to their facilities and be accessible themselves in an open, FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and equitable manner for excellent Open Science and Open Scholarship to be performed, shared and exploited.
- **Open Science Conduct and Outputs:** Simplify, clarify and improve consistency to enable and encourage the practice of Open Science.
- **Intellectual Property Rights:** Encourage open access to and reuse of research outputs by providing a comprehensive and coherent framework to protect Intellectual Property Rights (IPR).
- **Awareness and Skills:** Help develop the necessary awareness and skills for the EOSC.
- **Incentives:** Provide incentives for practising Open Science and embed open principles in recruitment, promotion and evaluation of researchers at all stages of their careers.
- **Policy Supporting Services:** Develop and operate Open Science Policy Supporting Services to support policy adoption and promote best practices.
- **Data Protection and Information Security:** Ensure EOSC Open Access research data use and reuse permit the rights and obligations of Data Protection Legislation (most notably the EU General Data Protection Regulation) to be achieved in a fair, transparent and accountable manner.
- **Procurement:** Ensure that aggregated procurement is utilised by the EOSC where appropriate when making resources available to the EOSC marketplace.

2.2 FAIR-Lady report from EOSC Executive Board Sustainability WG

Published in November 2020, the FAIR Lady report builds upon the work of the EOSC Sustainability Working Group started in July 2019 by the EOSC Executive Board [2]. The document explores possible means for sustaining EOSC beyond its initial phase and considers its financing model, legal vehicle, governance structure under the planned European Partnership with the EC as well as its regulatory and policy environment. Its main recommendation is to establish initially a Minimum Viable EOSC (MVE) addressing the needs of publicly funded researchers exploiting openly available data. Subsequent iterations should expand the EOSC to address usage beyond openly available FAIR data and engage a wider user base including the public sector and the private sector.

The report also documents a set of recommendations on funding schemes and business models towards a sustainable EOSC:

- **Establish an EOSC funding support team** dedicated to identifying and securing funds.
- **Raise awareness within the research communities of what EOSC-Core is and provide a clear mapping of the services it contains**
- **Promote wider use of cost-based accounting.** Service costing activities need to move beyond FTE based project accounting in order to establish more accurate estimates of costs for service operation and future development.
- **Virtual Access is a step in the right direction but needs improvement.** The Horizon 2020 virtual access funding mechanism encourages service providers to move beyond current project-based accounting approaches but needs to evolve further if it is to be more widely used in the longer-term.
- **EOSC requires Service Provider Aggregation,** at least in the short time range, as existing Service Providers (GEANT, EGI, EUDAT and OpenAIRE) have knowledge about the needs to be fulfilled and about a wide range of services relevant to EOSC
- **Long-term preservation of data** as digital preservation is not explicit in the context of EOSC and the roles, responsibilities and accountability for digital preservation are currently not clearly defined.
- **Pre-commercial Procurement.** The EOSC Association could coordinate and procure resources by implementing the more suitable norms and tools provided by the EU Procurement Code.
- **Consider EOSC sustainability as a whole.** Going beyond the focus on EOSC-Core is needed to assess how the funded EOSC related projects will be interacting with each other and to understand how these projects will contribute to the sustainability of EOSC.
- **EOSC as a “super” platform.** EOSC can become a “super-platform”, with the possibility of coordinating and connecting other existing platforms such as those operated by the service provider aggregators (GEANT, EGI, EUDAT and OpenAIRE) and the Research Infrastructures in a way that both they and EOSC would benefit by this strategy.
- **Enhancing the (business-related) skillset present in the EOSC community.** There is an abundance of highly skilled and motivated people working in the EOSC community to ensure it is a success. However, they are struggling with some of the more business-related skills, such as accounting, market analysis and business planning. It would benefit the community and

help to more efficiently achieve sustainable operations, if such skills could be engaged more readily in EOSC activities.

Additional recommendations for expansion of EOSC with engagement of the wider public and private sectors are also proposed:

- **Web of FAIR data.** For EOSC to have the greatest impact and reach to external stakeholders it must establish itself as the Web of FAIR data as its primary Unique Selling Point. Validation and interoperability of data in knowledge transfer and technology transfer are key to its centrality in the application (and collection) of research data from beyond the realms of academia.
- **INFRAEOSC-03 and INFRAEOSC-07 as environments for expansion.** The study has shown that the INFRAEOSC-03 and INFRAEOSC-07 funded projects should be used to initiate, implement, or prototype as appropriate, a series of actions recommended in this study that will enable the expansion of EOSC using the use-cases as concrete examples.
- **Alignment with EU marketplace initiatives.** Synergies with initiatives which are being developed in parallel, such as GAIA-X, EuroHPC, bloXberg, Industry Commons and the upcoming EIC marketplace have been highlighted by stakeholders and ought to be exploited, to save on duplication and speed up deployment of EOSC.

2.3 EOSC-Hub

The EOSC-Hub project ambition was to bring together multiple service providers to create a single contact point for European researchers and innovators to discover, access, use and reuse a broad spectrum of resources for advanced data-driven research.

Its Work Package 12 (WP12) focussed on the design of future business models and procurement frameworks for acquiring digital services from both publicly funded and commercial providers. Its main findings are documented in the EOSC-Hub deliverables 12.1 [7], 12.2 [8] and 12.3 [9].

2.3.1 EOSC-HUB deliverable 12.1

This document proposes a business model analysis in the EOSC context, with a specific focus on proposing mechanisms for acquiring digital services, based on the use cases where:

- a researcher may look to acquire services ‘on demand’,
- a departmental manager may look to acquire services for its constituent researchers to use,
- where resources can be procured in ‘bulk’.

The assumption in the analysis was that the customer/user always operates in a business-to-business (B2B) type of relationship and not as a consumer (as defined by the EU Consumer Rights Directive) for personal purposes.

The business model analysis identified three main models:

- In the first model, **an individual researcher or a small research group needs limited-scale access to commercial services** on an ad hoc basis. This model foresees that users will receive services free at the point of use while service providers are financially rewarded indirectly by funders.
- In the second model, **institutional usage is fulfilled via specific purchase-supply contracts between the service provider and institution**. It analyses the explicit terms that the EOSC Portal would need to capture to address any issues concerning contract privity, EU Procurement Directives compliance and other statutory legislative/regulatory implications of such a business relationship.
- In the third business model, **an aggregated procurement is considered to allow joint purchasing to collectively exploit existing pan-European mechanisms** and remove the need for repeated and costly procurement processes.

2.3.2 EOSC-Hub deliverable 12.2

This document focuses on issues associated with acquiring digital services for research in the EOSC [8].

Their analysis identifies the following key points:

- an **aggregation of demand and the application of centralised procurement** can provide access to markets, process efficiency, and value for users. However, the EC procurement directive has some elements that limit flexibility over the lifetime of an aggregated procurement regarding who can benefit. Changes to the policy or an option for the EOSC Legal Entity to commission resources/services could be considered.
- **Obligations and liabilities of parties involved in the supply chain** need to be carefully understood, be it the EOSC legal entity or another actor, for example, in the event of a GDPR breach or financial liability excess consumption of resources.
- The **use of vouchers** is to be considered to be valuable in driving the adoption of cloud services. However, the overhead required to do this may be disproportionate in manpower or the VAT peculiar to the treatment of vouchers.
- **Virtual access as a mechanism for recovering costs** in EC-funded projects is expected to be of benefit and could potentially further assist in enabling public-to-public collaborations.
- The **absence of public-to-public case studies** where the providing party wishes to seek remuneration for their service has constrained the recommendations, noting that such a construct can only exist in circumstances where the parties involved are subject to the EC procurement directive.

2.3.3 EOSC-Hub deliverable 12.3

The EOSC-Hub WP12 final deliverable[9] identifies and evaluates a set of business models (BM) for procuring services in EOSC and maps them to the EOSC ecosystem. The proposed BMs are classified into Public procurement (BM1, BM2 and BM3), Virtual Access (BM4), Cross-border pooling of resources (BM5 and BM6) and Public-to-public cooperation (BM7 and BM8):

- **BM1 is Public procurement with direct contract without a Framework Agreement (FA).** This model refers to the plain case of a public procurement, i.e., there will be a selection of the most appropriate providers for the services.
- **BM2 is a special case including a FA without a Central Purchasing Body (CPB).** This model refers to the case where there is a need of repetitive procurement for public institutions, through a broad framework agreement that gives more flexibility (more service orders for example). **Examples** of this BM are public research provider organisations procuring resources or services for their communities (e.g., NRENs or NGIs for networking, computing, storage infrastructures and services);
- **BM3 is a special case with demand aggregation and a Central Purchasing Body.** As in BM2, the contracting authority establishes a framework agreement for its own needs (not on behalf of others). However, the demand for common services in BM3 can be aggregated in order to get the best deals from suppliers in the market.
- **BM4, the Virtual Access (VA), mechanism is a specific financial instrument in “European Research Infrastructures (including e-Infrastructures).** The VA is provided as Free/open access via the Internet. No selection of users is imposed. The chosen access providers will take in charge the access for either services, or more broadly research infrastructure (access to scientific equipment, knowledge-based research, Data, etc.).
- **BM5, the Cross-border pooling of resources,** encourages fairness of resource sharing and increases the likelihood of serving data and services demands. The contributions can be based on scientific collaboration agreements such as the ones between thematic Research Infrastructures (ESFRI or others). The aim here is to implement research and innovation activities to enhance competitiveness and to tackle the societal challenges with the active engagement of Europe’s industry.
- **BM6, as a cross-border pooling of resources (In-kind + In-cash).** In this case, the in-kind contributions are complemented by in cash contributions, such as grants, EC funds, national funds, or other such as the ones supported by the ESFRI Roadmap process. **Examples** for this BM are the EOSC overall framework, and in particular the EOSC Partnership characterised by such a business model of joint in-Cash and in-Kind contributions from EC and MS/ACs.
- **BM7, the Public-to-public cooperation with cost recovery (part 1),** is an exemption to the directory, so there is no need to go through a competitive tender process or additional administrative burdens and costs. It is a cooperation between two or more public bodies that don’t have direct relationship, and where there is a need for co-working and cooperation for a common objective for the public interest.
- **BM8, a public-to-public cooperation with cost recovery (part 2),** is another variation of the directory, a vertical case where there is a direct relationship between the two public sector bodies. There is some kind of control: one of the two public bodies exercises control over the other, as if it was its own department.

The deliverable stresses that the tender requirements for the public procurement of EOSC Core and parts of EOSC Exchange in 2022 need to be analysed thoroughly in order for a business model to be selected. Particular attention should be given to flexibility and adapting to evolving requirements.

In this context, the deliverable proposes a set of recommendations:

- Joint efforts are needed between the EOSC-Future project, the EC, the EOSC Association, and the EOSC Steering Board for planning the migration from the grant-based approach to the tender-based procurement;
- A proactive preparation is highly recommended for all the relevant parties, either for Horizon Europe or for public procurement, with all the necessary legal and financial expertise needed;
- The possibility of switching from tenders to grants should also be available, if there is no sufficient engagement in tenders either from market players or from the industry sector. To mention that a joint consortium, if structured between research service providers and industrials, can boost the supply of services within the EOSC project;
- Business models need to be analysed and evaluated further on, as the role of the different EOSC governance body should be defined, maybe with an evaluation at intermediate stages of the project.

2.4 Models adopted by comparable initiatives outside Europe

It is important to consider EOSC construction in a broad international context. Parallel initiatives to create a web of FAIR data are under construction in other countries and continents. This subsection is dedicated to contributing additional elements from initiatives comparable to EOSC outside Europe, namely Africa, Australia, Canada, China and the United States.

2.4.1 Australian Research Data Commons

The Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) is a parallel initiative to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), supported by the Australian Government [11]. Its goal is to enable the Australian research community and industry to access nationally significant, leading edge data intensive e-Infrastructure, platforms, skills and collections of high-quality data. The ARDC vision is similar to that of EOSC. It aims to become a coherent research environment to enable researchers to find, access, contribute to and effectively use services to maximise research quality and impact.

ARDC (<https://ardc.edu.au/>) is also a company limited by guarantee, that brings together three legacy initiatives: Australian National Data Service (ANDS), National eResearch Collaboration Tools and Resources (Nectar) and Research Data Services (RDS). The ARDC as an organisation is not equivalent to the Australian Research Data Commons, just as any future EOSC legal entity is not the EOSC. Many more organisations are involved in implementing the vision of the Commons and delivering core data services.

Regarding its business model, the ARDC company is registered as a charity which means it does not operate for the profit, personal gain or other benefit of particular people. It receives most of its funding from the Australian government, about 30 million \$ in the last financial year to provide services that are free at the point of use by Australian researchers.

2.4.2 Digital Research Alliance of Canada

The Digital Research Alliance of Canada (<https://alliancecan.ca>) serves Canadian researchers, with the objective of advancing Canada's position as a leader in the knowledge economy on the international stage. By integrating, championing and funding the infrastructure and activities required for Advanced Research Computing (ARC), Research Data Management (RDM) and Research Software (RS), the Alliance aims at providing the platform for the research community to access tools and services faster than ever before.

Regarding its governance, The Alliance is a non-profit organisation funded by the Government of Canada. Its revenues come from the Ministry of Innovation, Science and Industry (11,25 million \$ in the financial year 2022) and from the membership fees (600.000 \$ in 2022).

2.4.3 Africa Open Science Platform

The Africa Open Science Platform (AOSP)³ was established in 2017 with the aim of positioning African scientists at the cutting edge of data intensive science by stimulating interactivity and creating opportunity through the development of efficiencies of scale, building critical mass through shared capacities, and amplifying impact through a commonality of purpose and voice.

At a regional level, this multi-institutional and multidimensional initiative mobilises the African scientific community in response to the opportunities and challenges presented by the digital world through open science. This ambitious platform provides African scientists with the necessary tools and concepts for practising open science, the stimulus for excellence in open science, and pathways to its application in the environment, business and society.

The AOSP is supported by South Africa's Department of Science and Innovation (DSI), the Committee on Data of the International Science Council, the Academy of Science of South Africa (Assaf), Bibliotheca Alexandrina, and other regional networks.

Currently, AOSP is overseen by an Interim Advisory Council comprising of volunteer senior experts in the field from African countries – including from Egypt, Kenya and Sierra Leone and South Africa, together with representation from International Science Council (ISC)⁴ and ISC Committee on Data (CODATA), and supported by a Technical Advisory Board. In 2020, South Africa's National Research Foundation NRF took on the hosting of the AOSP Project Office for a five-year period.

2.4.4 Open science initiatives in the United States of America

Many initiatives to promote open access and open data have originated in the United States. For instance, arXiv.org, one of the first and best known preprint servers, was developed in the US and has been maintained by Cornell University. The National Institutes of Health have made open access publishing in their PubMedCentral repository mandatory since 2008 (with a 12 month embargo). Since 2013, the US federal government requires public online availability of results of publicly funded

³ <https://aosp.org.za/about-us/>

⁴ <https://council.science/>

research within 12 months of publication in a journal [12]. Science.gov ⁵ is a gateway to U.S. government science information. The portal offers free access to research and development (R&D) results and scientific and technical information from scientific organisations across 13 federal agencies. Federal agencies are celebrating 2023 as a Year of Open Science, a multi-agency initiative across the federal government to spark change and inspire open science engagement through events and activities that will advance adoption of open, equitable, and secure science⁶.

To help build a culture of open science, NASA is championing the Open-Source Science Initiative (OSSI), a comprehensive program of activities to enable and support moving science towards openness, including policy adjustments, supporting open-source software, and enabling cyberinfrastructure. OSSI aims to implement NASA's Strategy for Data Management and Computing for Groundbreaking Science 2019-2024 ⁷, which was developed through community input.

2.4.5 Open science in China

The Chinese government has implemented a strongly centralised policy in 2018: the State Council has decreed that all scientific data generated in China must be submitted to government-sanctioned data centres before appearing in publications. The science ministry is responsible for creating a national data centre, but other ministries and local governments are expected to create their own centres as well ⁸.

More recently, efforts have started to explore models for open data sharing [13]. These efforts are mostly supported by public funding.

2.5 Summary of findings

Although far from complete, this overview of the work done within the context of EOSC Association and several EC Projects shows the wealth of efforts and reflections invested to understand the different options for EOSC business model. Comparison with other Open Science initiatives on different continents shows that similar governance models are adopted resulting in similar business models where public funding constitutes the main source of revenue.

In the next chapter, we are going to document the activities deployed in EOSC-Pillar to contribute to this collective effort.

⁵ <https://www.science.gov/>

⁶ <https://science.nasa.gov/open-science-overview>

⁷ https://science.nasa.gov/files/science-red/s3fs-public/atoms/files/SDMWG%20Strategy_Final.pdf

⁸ <https://www.science.org/content/article/china-asserts-firm-grip-research-data>

3 EOSC-Pillar results

This section describes EOSC-Pillar activities relevant to business models within task 4.5 and beyond. Its content is structured as follows:

- A first subsection focuses on analysing business models at national level as documented by different surveys conducted with and by EOSC-Pillar partners
- A second subsection is dedicated to exploring existing business models for services coming out of scientific communities that contributed to EOSC-Pillar. The aim of this activity was to analyse how sustainable business models would allow to keep these services alive for the communities at the end of the project.
- A third subsection documents the outcome of workshops co-organized by EOSC-Pillar where panels of representatives of inter-disciplinary communities shared their views and thoughts on business models.

3.1 Business models in national organisations

3.1.1 What does the National Survey tell us about the National Initiative business models (or financial sustainability models)?

The National Initiatives Survey objectives were to create a comprehensive picture of the research supporting infrastructure with state-of-the-art data to support the creation of the European Open Science Cloud. EOSC-Pillar D3.1 deliverable contains the main results in terms of frequency analysis. The summary, including methodological approach and survey design, was made publicly available on Zenodo and the corresponding dataset is available on the AUSSDA data repository [14].

EOSC-Pillar invited 2,204 organisations (funding bodies, universities, research infrastructures, and e-infrastructures) in five countries (Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, Italy) to participate in this ‘National Initiatives’ Survey. The representatives of 688 organisations (31%) responded to the survey and answered various questions following the questionnaire. All respondents received a common core of questions. Additionally, tailored sets of questions were dedicated to each target group. All respondents received only the questions relevant to them according to the classification of organisations in one of the target groups. Some of these questions were specifically dedicated to the “business models” topic and these questions were asked to the e-infrastructures⁹ and funding bodies. The results on business models are detailed in chapter 4.2 of the NIS. We are presenting here a summary of the results relevant for our work.

The aim of the set of questions regarding the e-infrastructures was to identify elements of their business models. Some questions targeted their sources of revenues (sources of funding, potential limitations of business models, e.g. due to the sources of funding, types of other revenues). Another objective was to identify the potential barriers that limit the expansion of the e-infrastructures’ services and whether and in what way they charge their users/clients for services as well as to better

⁹ E-infrastructures: including data repositories, data archives, data/ computing centres, grid infrastructure, HPC’s, NREN’s and national museums with digital archives

understand how e-infrastructures buy supplies or rent supplies, resources or services and what is their knowledge of the cost of the service(s) they provide.

In addition, the survey gives other insights about the customer segments (disciplines of users, user groups), communication and elements of the value proposition such as additional components to the services (support, training...) and maturity of the services (SLAs, security management...). Some elements of sustainability are also given.

Another part of the questionnaire targeted the funding bodies in order to identify what they fund and under what conditions they fund potential participants in EOSC such as e-infrastructures and research infrastructures (rules and conditions).

Another goal of the survey was to explore the potential differences between the five countries, but because the number of funding bodies who responded is rather small, it did not allow to make any analyses on a country level for this group.

In order to be consistent with the approach of the business models developed in this deliverable, the presentation of the NI survey results follows the structure of the “Business Model Canvas” that is presented in the next sections.

Revenues:

Respondents representing e-infrastructures were asked “Who recurrently provides funding to your organisation?”. This is a multiple choice question. Figure 2 presents their answers (mean across all countries).

Figure 2 (from [14]): e-infrastructures answers to “Who recurrently provides funding to your organisation?”
Multiple choice, mean across countries

We observe substantial differences across countries (see Figure 3): the most frequently mentioned provider of resources differs across countries. State/ministries are the most frequently indicated funding providers in Austria, Belgium and Germany. On the contrary, research institutions are the most frequently mentioned funding source in France. Italian e-infrastructures most frequently rely on European funds. Industry and SMEs is the least frequently indicated source of funding across countries.

Figure 3 (from [14]) : Sources of funding of the e-infrastructures in the EOSC-Pillar partner countries
 Note: target group: e-infrastructures; stacked dataset of all services; bars show percentages per country (e.g. the first bar shows that 38% of the e-infrastructures in Austria recurrently receive funding from research institution(s)); multiple choice question (so the percentages per country do not add to 100%), original categories: 'research institution(s)', 'university', 'state/ministry', 'region/ town', 'research communities', 'European funds', 'industry/small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs)', 'funding agencies/funding bodies', 'other'.

Another objective was to analyse whether e-infrastructures have sources of funding besides recurrent funding and what these sources of incomes are. The first question was: "Does your organisation acquire its own revenues other than funding?". 37% of the e-infrastructures answered they acquire their own revenues other than funding. They were asked "What are the sources of your own revenues other than funding?" (multiple choice question). Figure 4 provides the mean across all countries of their sources of funding. More details are available in D3.1 section 4.2.1.

Figure 4 (from [14]): What are the sources of your own revenues other than funding?

Note: question was asked to respondents representing e-infrastructures; multiple choice question, mean across all countries.

We also asked the 106 e-infrastructures who acquire their own revenues if their organisation charges users/clients for services. The average across countries is: 40% do NOT charge users, 49% charge users/clients for some services, 8% charge users for all services.

It is important to take into account in parallel the rules applied by the funders. Funding bodies were asked “What does your organisation fund?”. The main funding items are ‘human resources’ and ‘project based resources’ as 92% of the respondents chose these answers. Figure 5 (from [14]) shows the types of expenses that funding bodies fund.

Figure 5 (from [14]) : What funding bodies fund

Note: question was asked to funding bodies; multiple choice question; total percentages in all countries, N = 25.

The next question asked to the funding bodies was: “Does your organisation have rules for granting funds for e-infrastructures or research infrastructures based on the following aspects?”. This was a multiple choice question. Figure 6 visualises the different rules used by the funding bodies.

Figure 6 (from [14]): Rules for funding

Note: question was asked to funding bodies; multiple choice question; total percentages in all countries, N = 25.

Customer segment:

On average, across countries, e-infrastructures provide services most frequently to Natural Sciences communities (69%), followed by Humanities (45%), Engineering and Technology (43%), Medical and Health Sciences (38%), Social Sciences (38%), and finally Agricultural Sciences (30%). 6% of the e-infrastructures also indicated to provide other communities with services. Country differences are explained in [14] page 56.

User groups of services are distributed as follows: (researchers based at) universities are by far the most frequent users of the services provided by e-infrastructures. Across countries, 86% of the e-infrastructure representatives indicated that universities and their associated researchers use their services frequently or very frequently. Ranked second are (researchers of) non-university research institutions and students: on average, 70% of the respondents indicated that these groups use their services (very) frequently. The remaining four groups of users use the services substantially less. On average, between 20% and 25% of the service providers indicated that (researchers of) private, commercial institutions, governmental institutions (e.g. census bureaus), professionals and citizen scientists use their services (very) frequently. Besides, the percentage of respondents who indicated that they 'don't know' how frequently these groups use their services or who skipped the question increases substantially. 6% of the respondents indicated on average that 'other' groups of users use their services (very) frequently.

Activities restriction:

The e-infrastructures were asked if their organisation restricts access to its services to one or more of the following groups? Figure 7 visualises the different criteria applied by e-infrastructures to restrict access to their services. Important findings are that the most frequently used criteria for access varies across countries and that more than a third of the e-infrastructures does not apply any restriction. More detailed insights are available in [14].

Figure 7 (from [14]): Limitation of the access to the e-infrastructures services based on certain criteria (in%)
 Note: target group: e-infrastructures; stacked dataset of all services; percentages per country, multiple choice question (so the percentages per country do not add to 100%), original categories: 'users or communities approved by the funding body (e.g. due to regional or research topic restrictions)', 'users selected by competition', 'members of certain communities or organisations (e.g. virtual organisations)', 'national users', 'no access restrictions', 'not applicable', 'other'.

In addition the e-infrastructures were asked “Does your organisation currently have policies, procedural and/or technical barriers that limit the expansion of your services to further user groups?”

The average across countries is: 38%: yes ; 47%: no; 11%: don't know; 5%: no response

Costs:

There is nothing about cost optimization in the survey, but questions investigate what knowledge about service costs the providers may have, or what other relevant information they may be able to collect [14]

The e-infrastructures' answer to the question “How do you buy supplies, resources or services?” show that e-infrastructures most frequently buy or rent supplies, resources or services by means of

tender (57%), followed by pre-negotiated procurements (29%) and the category 'without tender' (16%) [14].

Do e-infrastructures know the unit cost of the services they offer? This is important in the perspective of EOSC if these e-infrastructures are willing to participate. Although the business model of EOSC is not clear yet – besides the point of the services being 'free in point of use' (services are provided free of charge for users) – some remuneration mechanisms for the participating service providers and data providers should be defined. But if they lack the means of quantifying costs, clearly this raises the question of how to quantify the remuneration. The aim of the single choice question 'Does your organisation know the unit cost of your services? If yes, what is the granularity?' is to investigate this point. 322 e-infrastructures were asked this question. Figure 8 shows the results by country. It reveals substantial differences across countries.

Figure 8 (from [14]): Does your organisation know the unit cost of your services? If yes, what is the granularity?

All these figures refer to e-infrastructures and funding bodies that answered this survey, that are 44 % out of the 727 e-infrastructures invited, and 25 funding bodies out of the 91 invited. Perceptions of and expectations from EOSC was also a topic of the NI survey. The results are that 18 of 26 funding bodies' representatives indicated to be (very) familiar with EOSC as did on average 48% of the e-infrastructures. Country differences are substantial for e-infrastructures. Between 67% (e-infrastructures) and 76% (funding bodies) of the respondents expect that their organisation will benefit very much or somewhat from EOSC. On average, 40% of the e-infrastructures are already contributing to EOSC and 14% of the e-infrastructures' representatives indicated that they do not know whether their organisation already contributes to EOSC. We are now going to compare these results to the outcome of a survey focussed on organisations already contributing to the EOSC set up.

3.1.2 Results of the TTF survey for the different EOSC-Pillar countries

3.1.2.1 Introduction

To coordinate a consultation process of National Initiatives, in particular those acting as national representatives in the context of EOSC, Task 4.5 collaborated with a Transversal Task Force (TTF), to coordinate the survey efforts carried out by different EOSC-Pillar's tasks: T4.1 on Policy and legal framework, Task 4.3 on Consolidation of National Initiatives, Task 4.5 on Sustainable Business Models, Task 2.2 on Concertation with the EOSC governance and related EOSC initiatives, and Task 7.1 on Guidance on procedures for integrating services. The list of contacts was provided by WP3 colleagues, selecting among the respondents to the National Initiatives Survey those who had provided their consent to be further involved and were National Initiative contacts or service providers. The TTF aimed at gathering information on:

- policy on open science and open data
- the expected role of the EOSC-Association and the EOSC-related projects in the above processes
- the services relevant at the national level with respect to onboarding into the EOSC
- the different ways for implementing a “federation” of services
- business models elements and issues for supporting sustainable national and trans-national data, compute and open science services

A list of questions on policies and business model and issues for supporting sustainable data, compute and open science services, was elaborated in collaboration with T4.1 (for Legal and Policy elements), with WP7 T7.1 (for Service Level Agreements) and with the support of WP3. The TTF functioned from December 2020 to June 2021.

The set of questions was aimed at gathering quantitative and qualitative information on business models of national initiatives and service providers (e.g. data suppliers and aggregators, enablers): such as costs, income streams and revenues, funding structures, organisational design, etc. The aim was to identify current practices and barriers faced in relation to creating, implementing and operating sustainable business models.

For each country the TTF decided to consult the national/mandated organisation plus national thematic research infrastructures, trying to cover different disciplines. A total of 23 interviews were carried out between mid-April and the end of June 2021: 5 in Austria, 2 in Belgium, 4 in France, 5 in Germany and 6 in Italy.

This section describes the results of the survey for the different countries.

3.1.2.2 Belgium

FRIS

In Belgium, the Flanders Research Information Space (FRIS) was interviewed by the TTF. FRIS is the regional portal on researchers and their research in Flanders¹⁰. It aggregates information on

¹⁰ See the portal at <https://researchportal.be/en>

research, research organisations, publications, projects and plans on collecting information on PhD theses, patents, datasets and metadata from research infrastructure and in the future. Access to the FRIS portal is open and free under an open licence, with exception of access to confidential data. Access to public data is available through their portal. Additionally, the public data is accessible through a consumer service which allows other systems access to retrieve, incorporate and process data in their own systems through an open API. Flanders have various reporting obligations to the federal government and to the European Union on research conducted in Flanders, which is funded from various sources. The fact that the data for these obligations will be centralised provides administrative simplification. FRIS has been established as close cooperation between the Department of Economics, Science and Innovation of the Flemish Government and the knowledge institutions in Flanders, i.e. Flemish universities, higher education colleges, strategic research centres, and other scientific institutions. FRIS plays an instrumental role in connecting Flemish research to EOSC. As a regional e-infrastructure, FRIS is funded by the Flemish government since 2008. Government support guarantees a sustainability-strategy for the long term, sustainable operations, keeping track of new technologies and changes in business models. A study was done on cost-efficiency which will be implemented as the e-infrastructure matures and advised setting up a general infrastructure with a possibility for microservices and on-demand requests to reduce costs. Performance, sustainability and data-quality are top-priorities in the development of the infrastructure. Since the infrastructure is publicly funded, no access restriction on the use of the services and no costs are associated with the use of the FRIS platform or any of their services.

Belnet

Belnet was selected by the CIS-CfS as the mandated organisation for Belgium within the EOSC association. Since Belgium is a federated country where research is a regional capacity, coordination is established through a bottom-up process through the Open Science working group of CIS-CFS (Commission International Cooperation-Commission Federal Cooperation). As such, the mandated organisation represents the federated research landscape where Belnet functions as a representative of the different stakeholders. Within the EOSC association, they represent Belgian interests and positions.

Belnet is a federal government organisation and belongs to the Federal Science Policy (BELSPO). As a National Research and Education Network (NREN), Belnet is one of the few research-oriented infrastructures in Belgium that is national in scope. Belnet is a data network provider that has an important role to play as a Service Provider with services focused on connectivity and security. They stimulate the deployment of the knowledge and information society by providing and maintaining high quality innovative network infrastructures with associated services. It represents the interests of all players that form a part of the Belgian research landscape. Furthermore Belnet will take care to provide a variety of value-added services to the EOSC and is already connected through the GÉANT network. They operate under a hybrid business model of public funds and market-driven mechanisms of income i.e. basic services such as network connection are centrally resourced by public funds. But specific services function under a paid access-model. This can be a direct paid contribution or a paid membership of governance. As such Belnet combines central public funding, funding from endowments and paid access, depending on the service, project and the (type of) client.

3.1.2.3 France

In **France**, 4 organisations were interviewed by the TTF: EOSC-FRANCE, a working group created by the French MESRI to propose a mandated organisation for EOSC-Association and to coordinate engagement towards EOSC in France, and 3 thematic national e-infrastructures, GENCI, Data Terra and IFB. The 3 NI are publicly funded, with small participation to National or European projects. Cost studies are performed for all NI by each entity part of the infrastructure but without really considering service unit costs. If they are calculated, the method depends on the entity delivering the service, and so no consistent view of services unit costs is available at the infrastructure level. It is noticed that entities providing computing services are more advanced with service cost evaluation (e.g. IFB, GENCI). No business model is available for the 3 NI, but IFB HPC cluster federation has developed its own (basic package free but pricing mechanism based on data volume and computing time for more extensive use). However, each NI is reflecting upon their business model, and key points to take into account. Among those, energy consumption is identified as a potential barrier, as well as services scalability towards larger user communities. Environmental footprint is also of high interest. Collaboration with the private sector is also of concern and will be explored by Data Terra infrastructure to share thematic services supported by the PIA3 Gaïa Data project. No NI is outsourcing its activities, even if Data Terra could consider reaching out to cloud providers, with the exception of GENCI which delegates some services among entities part of GENCI's shareholders. EOSC-FRANCE, due to its status and recent creation, had not discussed business models aspects at the time of the interview.

GENCI

GENCI is a French numerical e-infrastructure with objectives to increase the use of high performance computing (HPC) and numerical simulation across all scientific and industrial fields. GENCI implements the national strategy by deploying HPC resources in the three national computing centres (CEA, CNRS, CINES) and making the systems available for French researchers. GENCI is a "civil society" owned by French ministry MESRI and other French research institutes, universities and public organisations. At European level, GENCI is the hosting member and one of the resource providers of PRACE. GENCI's HPC services are listed in PRACE and FENIX catalogues of services, and available in the EOSC marketplace. GENCI's funding comes mainly from governmental budgets, and, to a lesser extent, from national and European projects in which the infrastructure participates. Services' unit costs are calculated for internal use and the method differs between shareholders, so there is no consistent view of services unit costs at infrastructure level. There is a potential for improvement in terms of energy efficiency. This type of cost could be better predicted with the establishment of a benchmark code portfolio. The environmental footprint is another component GENCI considers as a barrier to take into account in future business models. GENCI does not act as a facilitator between direct users and other external providers, and does not outsource its activities except for a small amount of services that are delegated among GENCI's shareholders entities. The decision-making model is fully centralised.

DATA TERRA

Data Terra is a French distributed e-infrastructure for environment and Earth system domains.. It is composed of 26 partners (CNRS, CNES, INRAE, IFREMER, IRD, Météo-France, ...) organised in 4

thematic data clusters for each compartment of the Earth system (AERIS for atmosphère, ADATIS for Ocean, Form@Ter for solid Earth, THEIA for continental surfaces). Each data cluster provides a range of services (FAIR, on-demand treatments) to facilitate data discovery, access and uses and harmonise data management across the data services centres according to international standards and recommendations. Data Terra is funded by the French Ministry as well as French organisations and research institutes that are part of the Data Terra consortium. There are no permanent revenues from the services Data Terra provides. In the context of the Gaïa Data project, funded by the French Ministry on a PIA3/France 2030 grant, Data Terra plans to build different kinds of business models depending on users and applications with a specific focus on . Collaboration with the private sector will be explored, through provision of on-demand services or added-value products to private companies (e.g. Thales) or partnerships and scientific collaboration (e.g. SPATIAL) for better operational aspects. A cost survey for Data Terra infrastructure is performed every 3 years in the context of the National Research Infrastructure roadmap. However, there is a lack of expertise for evaluating the costs of services, further investment is planned in this regard. Mutualisation of manpower, expertise and resources should be considered to optimise costs, with centralised softwares to be deployed in a uniform way. Ensuring energy sobriety is also a point to take into account for the business model. Outsourcing activities to cloud providers could be considered.

IFB

IFB is the French national bioinformatics e-infrastructure as well as a research infrastructure. It is also the French node for ELIXIR ESFRI. IFB federates national or regional bioinformatics platforms providing direct services to biologists for their research (data, software & tools and IT resources dedicated to life sciences). IFB also provides training (e.g. use of high volume data), support to projects. IFB offers services to the French community which are articulated with those of ELIXIR, but the relation is not automatic. There is no connection with EOSC yet although there are links with EOSC-related projects (EOSC-Pillar, EOSC Life) where developments of services are discussed. IFB is funded by the French Ministry budget under a PIA3 grant. There are ongoing discussions about IFB business model key aspects: which pricing to apply, the possible differences between user categories (French academics, European Academics, Outside Academia...), especially to offer services across borders. The real cost is proposed for non academics. IFB is operating an ICT infrastructure on its own resources and in partnership with other structures (e.g. collaboration with Universities or computing/data centres). There is a strong focus on cloud activities in collaboration with France-Grilles & EGI. The IFB Cluster federation has established a business model recently. The basic package is free, and for more extensive use, a pricing has been established (based on both data volume and computing time). This should be put into effect in 2021.

3.1.2.4 Germany

For the analysis of the German situation, focus was put on the rapid developments around NFDI and GAIA-X and the accompanying views regarding among others the future plans for sustainable data services. For an overview of business models taken from over 40 examples of different scientific disciplines the reader is invited to read the report of the 'Rat für Informations Infrastrukturen' (<http://rfii.de>) [<https://nbn-resolving.org/urn:nbn:de:101:1-2020052673>] published in Sept 2021 just after the interviews discussed below.

In interviews, the director of NFDI and several representatives of NFDI consortia lend their views on funding and sustainability of the NFDI infrastructure. Their comments are not necessarily related to the consortium they represent because the questions on financial aspects and business models do not really differ across disciplines. One expectation is that the NFDI and its prospective services will be terminated once its objective is fulfilled and funding stops. There is currently no system in place that ensures specific access to specific stakeholders based on their contributions/payments. Also, the cost of services is not quantified, though many in NFDI are aware that data is a resource, and recognise the need to quantify it. There are no outsourcing activities, not even IT components. It was acknowledged by the representative of the NFDI4earth consortium, that the new factor of supranational infrastructures, [ESFRI, EOSC] are able to provide part of the resources and services which must be factored in with the different funding mechanisms in the countries. How services will be funded in the long term is still being discussed in NFDI. Currently, there are no plans for payment models.

The representative of the International Data Spaces working at the Fraunhofer IWM institute was not very familiar with EOSC, but stressed the importance of collaboration and the importance of inclusion of industry for running services to succeed. He stressed the importance of noted that one should adhere to open standards and clear any legal aspects beforehand.

3.1.2.5 Austria

AUSSDA

The Austrian Social Science Data Archive is a data infrastructure for the social science community in Austria and offers a variety of research support services. These include data archiving and management, data preparation, data access and data search as well as advice on licences and data protection for the purpose of data sharing.

AUSSDA is financed by in-kind services provided by participating partners and direct financial contributions from participating partners. There is no sale of paid services. From today's perspective, AUSSDA considers this business model to be sustainable. At the moment, there are no plans to change the financing model. However, the aim is to increase income by expanding the consortium. Risks with regard to sustainable financing of the organisation could occur when contracts are terminated or the consortium does not grow. Possibilities for cost reduction: Work in data preparation can only be reduced if self-services are used more often. Costs in technology (IT) could be reduced if more organisations could agree on central providers and the same software stack. At the moment, AUSSDA procures only a few external services.

ARCHE

ARCHE stands for A Resource Centre for the Humanities and is a service for the long-term digital archiving of data and their metadata from the humanities. ARCHE makes this data public and accessible.

There is a reasonable division of costs at ARCHE: core staff (technical, administrative and conceptual development of ARCHE) is funded by the Austrian Academy of Sciences (OeAW). The curation of data is financed by the respective projects but does not generate any revenue. As an external service,

ARCHE facilitates the generation of backup copies (so-called bitstream preservation) via an external network. ARCHE is not planning to establish any paid services. Currently, the archive sees no need to change its business model. From ARCHE's point of view, the effort involved in data curation, and thus the staff could be reduced to some extent by further automating the workflows, although this would mean increased human resources beforehand. ARCHE believes that human validation is indispensable for the quality of the data and cannot be entirely replaced.

GAMS

GAMS stands for Humanities Asset Management System. The repository is operated by the Institute Centre for Information Modeling. The centre is part of the University of Graz (Faculty of Humanities). GAMS is compliant with OAIS (Open Archival Information System) and offers long-term archiving as well as the assignment of persistent identifiers. It also makes data available for aggregation.

Funding is largely provided by externally funded research, while the limited permanent staff is funded by the repository's sponsoring institution. Paid services are not planned for GAMS. In the course of its existence, the volume of third-party funding has multiplied, leading to a certain asymmetry with regard to the permanent staff which is perceived as a potential risk in funding. GAMS does not see any possibilities for cost reduction, as the repository almost exclusively incurs personnel costs which cannot be reduced. Only open source software is used and external services are not used except for internal cooperation for servers and storage. GAMS sees no need to change its business model.

VSC

VSC is a supercomputer that researchers can use when they need extremely high computing power for their projects. The VSC is affiliated with the Vienna University of Technology. The most common uses of the VSC are high-performance computing in batch processing, support for users and the continuing training program.

VSC is funded by contributions from partner universities. To a lesser extent, it also generates income by selling computing time to other universities. Overall, paid services play only a minor role at VSC, although one or two services that are currently provided for free could become paid services in the future. The cost structure is reasonably optimised for both TU Wien and VSC. In terms of cost reduction, it would be a possible and sensible step for the host institution to rely more on joint facilities, developments and structures of several or all Austrian universities, such as the VSC in the area of HPC. From the VSC's point of view, there is little scope for changing the business model due to legal constraints. Within the framework of the EuroCC Competence Centre, VSC will increasingly approach users outside the scientific sector.

3.1.2.6 Italy

Five national infrastructures and ICDI, the Italian Computing and Data Infrastructure, appointed by the Italian Ministry of Research as the mandated organisation in the EOSC Association were selected by the TTF. These NIs are members of ICDI: Area Science Park, Elettra Sincrotrone Trieste, BBMRI.it, INAF and INFN.

Regarding the answers given for the 'business model' section, **ICDI** could not provide any elements, because its activities are currently on a voluntary basis. It is legally represented by GARR and members participate by signing a Memorandum of Understanding.

All five NIs are financed by national and/or regional public funds. We have noticed that, while when an infrastructure is offering analysis and computing services there is a more precise idea of the unit costs of the resources and in general, we are still a long way from developing a comprehensive business model. However, the relationship with international projects and infrastructures, whether connected to EOSC or not, helps in the identification of costs for maintaining and sharing the service.

Area Science Park is a public research body that hosts a Genomics and Epigenomics Platform, a facility dedicated to the analysis of sequences on DNA and RNA and genotyping (microarrays), and the ORFEO (Open Research Facility for Epigenomics and Other) data centre, providing a cloud-based infrastructure offering HPC/AI computation and storage. Part of the sequencers are linked with the CERIC-ERIC (Central European Research Infrastructure Consortium), a research infrastructure integrating and providing open access to some of the best facilities in Europe, to help science and industry advance in all fields of materials, biomaterials and nanotechnology. The data centre ORFEO is not yet linked with EOSC, but the plan is to join both EOSC and Elixir.it. They are currently evaluating the unit costs for all services. In doing this there is no lack of expertise, an issue could be a lack of time and commitment by scientists. Concerns are actually “aiuti di stato” (“state aid”) regulation toward commercial users. Improvements can be done in extracting costs from the database's development and in offering training and users support. Long term maintenance is not yet clear in terms of equipment renewal.

Elettra - Sincrotrone Trieste S.C.p.A. is a non-profit Share Company (Società Consortile per Azioni) of national interest pursuant to Law 370/99 of the Italian Republic. The company, which was established in 1987, manages the synchrotron light source Elettra and the free electron laser FERMI. Elettra is an open research infrastructure, with half users from Italy and half users worldwide. More than 300 researchers work at Elettra. It is the representative entity of Italy in CERIC-ERIC (Central European Research Infrastructure Consortium). Elettra ICT infrastructure is connected to EOSC through PaNOSC and ExPaNDS projects. The unit cost per hour of light is calculated very precisely: moreover they have very low indirect costs, all activities are managed.

BBMRI.it is the Italian node of BBMRI-ERIC, a European research infrastructure for biobanking. It has been established with a joint effort by the Ministry of Health and the Ministry of University & Research and it involves ISS (National Institute of Health), CNR, Universities, Hospitals, IRCCS - institutes of health care and research - and Patient Organizations - POs. It brings together all the main players from the biobanking field – researchers, biobanks, industry, and patients – to boost biomedical research and make new treatments possible. It is funded by the Ministry of Research (MUR) through ordinary funds (FOE) of CNR. The Ministry of Health provides support paying the fee to access the EU infrastructure. The BBMRI.it value proposition is about the personalised medicine approach based on biobanking data results to improve all the processes of health care, supporting best practices in diagnosis and cure. BBMRI.it is a distributed research infrastructure with a highly data-centric infrastructure, based on biobanking that stores biological tissues that are linked to patient data. The cost recovery of TNA (TransNational and virtual Access) is calculated at the EU level. The cost recovery for the sample is accepted. However, access fees alone will not be sufficient

to cover the cost recovery of the biobank. Samples are preserved for future research and could be considered an investment for personalised medicine that could be compensated in the future with the development of new services: long-term preservation of the infrastructure is thus essential, and public funding is perceived as the optimal funding stream to achieve this. Opportunities for new business models rely on the development of innovative services for elaborating data and training.

INAF is the Italian National Institute of Astrophysics. It is a national research infrastructure collaborating with the International Virtual Observatory Alliance (IVOA, <https://www.ivoa.net/>) and several other intergovernmental organisations and projects such as for example the European Southern Observatory (ESO), the Square Kilometre Array Observatory (SKAO) and the Cherenkov Telescope Array (CTA). INAF is managing two ICT infrastructures: CHIPP (Calcolo HTC in INAF – Progetto Pilota) and IA2 (Italian centre for Astronomical Archive). They are not yet connected with EOSC, but there are mid-term plans to do it when it will be more clear which services are relevant for EOSC. INAF was approved as a provider in the EOSC Portal in May 2021. They have never quantified unit costs of services because INAF does not offer external services: at the moment all the services are public; they're working internally on archiving services and they don't have outsourced activities. When they offer external services they could be interested in receiving support from EOSC for the definition of the agreement.

INFN is the research infrastructure for High Energy Physics in Italy. It is part of the international infrastructure supporting HEP experiments. INFN is managing and operating an ICT infrastructure supporting not only HEP experiments but other INFN research activities; there is interest in connecting this infrastructure to EOSC as part of a federated environment supporting similar ICT tools in a variety of multi-disciplinary activities. Some services have already been onboarded into the EOSC catalogue. The access is today membership/policy-based, with however a small fraction of the resources in wide non-priority access. The experience in calculating the unit cost of INFN resources is limited, i.e. INFN did this exercise for the EGI-ACE and DICE projects only. It was quite difficult due to the criteria defined for this calculation which require strict accounting of all items. For some of them, such as the manpower devoted to the operation of the services, we cannot do it because it is impossible to have a very fine-grained accounting. The current EC criteria for the unit cost calculation look quite artificial because they do not consider how the real data centres work. INFN sees potential for improvement in terms of costs, because different parts of the community use different tools without real need, thus increasing the cost of maintenance, support, and operation.

3.1.2.7 Summary of findings

From the interviews, the following summary can be extracted for **Austria and Germany**. **Funding resources** come from direct state funding or from project-oriented funding and other third-party funding. Some **income from the infrastructures is generated via paid-for services** but this model is minor. The organisations indicate possibilities for increased revenue streams, e.g. by providing services outside the target customer group or by service provisioning. Although **that model is currently not part of NFDI it may be in the future**: some infrastructures hint that this may have an impact on the role of the organisations in NFDI, and thus require an update of the business model.

The situation in **Belgium** is similar to that in Germany. **Government funding is the main source of sustainable funding** for both services interviewed. However, Belnet has a more diversified business model. Because of its unique market position and through its economies of scale for providing and maintaining high-quality network infrastructures and associated services to meet the specific needs of higher education, research and public sector administration in Belgium, it both has an **income through invoiced services and public funding**.

The situation in **France** is also similar by many aspects to the situation in Austria, Belgium and Germany. The National Initiatives interviewed **rely mainly on government funding and try to diversify funding sources**. The recently created EOSC-France initiative is initiating the reflection on its business model.

In **Italy**, many infrastructures are **funded through ministries or one specific research institution**, and in some cases serve the needs of a specific community. When this is the case, and **especially if the reference community is mainly at a national scale, there is little interest in developing a complete business model**. Some elements thereof, though, like computation of unit costs, are deemed essential and many organisations have ongoing activities towards achieving this. In this respect, organisations note the benefit of **being part or being connected to a European-scale infrastructure**, as it **provides both an incentive and standard methods for calculation**: at the same time, however, some note that such methods may be hardly applicable within some contexts, like ICT services, where cost items (e.g., personnel costs) may be shared among several services.

There is **an explicit wish to help support and connect with the EOSC Core services**¹¹. At the same time, it was said that **possibilities for cost reduction through improved automation and self-service** are possible. Self-service would transfer the costs to the scientists themselves. The fact that (smaller) service providers would sacrifice usability and service features over costs must be accounted for when deploying paid-for services. (e.g. by keeping stakeholders in the operational decision process by making them members of the service-providing organisation). Services and service operations (including staff) are sometimes also dependent on non-structural funding and there are diverse dependencies of the service providing organisations on volatile income. e.g. grants: this is a concern, especially in connection to the long-term sustainability of the infrastructure/service, and some note that public funding would largely be useful in this respect. Finally, the funding of organisations to deliver services should be earmarked and dedicated to the respective service.

3.2 Business models for communities and generic services

One of the objectives of this activity was to investigate the existing business models within the project and in particular within the use cases which provide new services for the communities represented in WP6 and the ready-to-use services offered in WP7. The aim was to identify potentially sustainable business models to keep these services alive for the communities at the end

¹¹ <https://eosc-portal.eu/news/new-services-coming-eosc-core>

of the project. The achievement of this objective proved to be complex because the business models of the selected use-cases involve multiple partners with different approaches and constraints.

Instead of identifying and defining potential business models from multiple stakeholder use cases, we focused on **a set of ready-to-use services** as well as **use-cases with a small number of organisations**, also including the additional use-cases that were selected in the context of the Open Call led by T6.10.

This activity involved liaising with communities around EOSC-Pillar to leverage on a larger research community to increase the uptake of guidelines and recommendations for business models.

To collect the required information, we performed guided interviews using an **adapted version (see Figure 9) of the Business Model Canvas**, described in the methodology section [3]. The canvas is a strategic management template providing an overview of the crucial processes, resources, and infrastructure. Osterwalder and Pigneur [4] believed that a business model can best be described through nine basic building blocks that cover the four main areas of a business: customers, offer, infrastructure, and financial viability. This tool resembles a painter's canvas to give an impression on how organisations intend to make money.

The interviews were conducted from March to July 2022. Between two and six people from management and implementation out of the different use cases participated in the Business Models Canvas interviews conducted by members of T4.5. In total, representatives of 10 services have been interviewed.

Due to the pandemic situation, it was not possible to conduct the workshops in person. The approach described before, where a large print of the Business Model Canvas is used to collect input of a group of people via sketching and using Post-it® notes or board markers, had to be adapted for online workshops.

SUMMARY Business Model Workshop for XXX on the XXX

Figure 9. Screenshot of the business model canvas adaptation that was used by T4.5 in the workshops with Open Science IT Services. The “XXX” in the header were tailored for each workshop.

A document containing the Business Model Canvas (see Figure 9) and additional guiding questions for each of the 9 fields (see Appendix) was created for the online workshops. This document was sent in advance to the interviewees of the selected Services, so they were prepared for the type of questions. The workshops were then conducted in the fashion of interviews. The T4.5 members asked questions regarding all fields of the Business Model Canvas and took notes of the answers by the interviewees. Since most of the interviewees had little to no prior experience with studying the business model aspects of their services, elaborate explaining and repeated focused questioning was necessary to work out answers to all or most of the fields of the Business Model Canvas. The interviews took sometimes up to several hours. After the workshop, the interviewers filled out the Business Model Canvases based on the notes taken during the interviews.

The data was collected in the table (Business Model Canvas) and in additional notes in the document and only accessible to members of T4.5. Before data collection and analysis began, all team members agreed to keep the collected data confidential and to present the results anonymously. The team reviewed the workshop documentation and analysed the cases according to the most suitable patterns.

The next section presents the results of the Business Model Canvas workshops in the context of the selected literature. The selected articles had an impact on our analysis and are important for the interpretation of the data. However, only certain aspects can be considered. Conducting a research project means making one's own choices from a wide range of issues and approaches, leaving out much that could still be important: the choices made are shaped by the research interest and the limitations due to the confidentiality of the data collected (this condition was stated by all of the

interviewees). Therefore, we have also chosen general examples to illustrate the different patterns. It should also be noted that these results are not easily transferable. They are based on the experiences and attitudes of specific interviewees and ten use cases. Conceptualizations relevant to the themes of T4.5 are presented below to allow for alignment between theory and our findings.

In total, **five Data-as-a-Service, four Software-as-a-Service, and three Platform-as-a-Service models were analysed**, even though most use-cases provide a mixed service (see statistic on value proposition below).

3.2.1 Qualitative analysis of the business model survey

As it has been made explicit by all the interviewees that the content of the interviews should remain confidential and anonymous, we analysed the interviews by aligning the answers to high level topics which will prevent identification of a specific organisation.

Based on these higher level concepts, we can provide some statistical presentation of the answers. For this analysis, we are presenting the various answers aggregated for each of the elements of the Business Model Canvas. Unless otherwise stated, all answers allowed multiple choices.

The selected services/organisations offer various types of **value propositions**: data deposition (40%), data archiving (30%), data analytics (40%), computing (20%), data access (60%), data aggregation (20%), data documentation (20%).

These services are made available for the following **types of users**: researchers and research institutions (100%), industry (50%), government (20%), libraries (10%), citizens (10%), students/teachers (30%), public organisations (10%). Out of the 10 services, 5 services have a mixed target user including research organisations and private sector. In addition, 40% of the services focus on specific scientific communities while the others are generic and domain agnostic.

For all the services, the **key resources** necessary to maintain and further develop the services are Human Resources (technical expertise) and IT infrastructure (hard- and software, networks and services). Additional key resources may be necessary such as office space (30%) or specific software (10%).

In terms of **Key activities**, we found the following activities: support and training (80%), service operation and maintenance (100%), consultancy (20%), data preservation (20%), data curation (30%), software development and customisation (40%). These activities are resource-intensive especially with respect to human resources. It is therefore obvious that the main item in the cost structure for these services is human resources (100%) followed by infrastructure/hardware (70%), communication (30%) and software (10%).

The organisations providing the considered services have established partnerships with research organisations and infrastructures (100%). In a few cases, users were considered as their **key partners** (20%), as well as software providers (20%).

Finally, the **revenue streams** leveraged to sustain their services is often a mixture of national funding (30%), in kind contribution of the host institution (50%) or institutional funding (20%), as well as publicly funded research projects (EU and national, 90%) and commercially funded projects (40%).

3.2.2 Proposed business models

The aim of the analysis was to identify the underlying business model patterns of specific services to get a better understanding how they can be sustained. The patterns identified from the interviews are summarised in Table 2 for three types of services which correspond to the value proposition of the different services investigated i.e. Data-as-a-Service, Software-as-a-Service and Platform-as-a-Service. Overall, five different business model patterns were recognized: advertising, commissioning, pay-per-use, subscription, and public funding. As the public funding pattern has been addressed by various projects such as EOSC Hub (see the introduction for more information), we chose to focus on the remaining four business model patterns.

	Public funding	Advertising	Commissioning	Pay-per-use	Subscription
Data-as-a-Service	x			x	x
Software-as-a-Service	x				x
Platform-as-a-Service	x	x	x	x	x

Table 2. Overview of the discovered business model patterns for Open Science IT Services.

Advertising conveys supportive messages from third parties to consumers, who usually pay for them. Mostly, advertising refers to messages in the form of banners, texts, images, and videos [15]. In the context of Platform-as-a-Service, for example, the internet service provider Google offers various online services.

The company generates valuable customer information that is in turn used for personalised advertising [16]. In line with the literature, advertising seems to be promising for Platform-as-a-Service models as all scientists could get access to the latest research data for free ([17]; [18]). A prerequisite for the attraction of advertisers is a crucial number of users. Therefore, advertising might be less appropriate in the introduction phase of these services. However, in the growth phase, when the number of users expands, research-related advertisers could be attracted to place their messages [18]. However Todri et al. in 2020 [19] pointed out that users are quickly annoyed by advertisements. Consequently, their frequent use could decrease, which would hinder the exchange

and creation of knowledge and thus the development of scientific innovations. Hence, advertising should be used with caution.

Commissioning is based on percentage fees deducted from the purchase of goods and services usually paid by third-party sellers [15]. Amazon Marketplace, for example, offers third-party sellers the ability to offer their sales to a wide range of customers. In exchange, Amazon obtains a percentage revenue share for each sale. Depending on the service, the fee ranges from 6.00% to 45.00% [20]. For Open Science Platform-as-a-Service models, a fee could be charged for each transaction on the platform. However, like advertising, commissioning requires a minimum number of users. Therefore, it can only be applied in the growth phase of the services, when the number of users is higher [21].

Pay-per-use refers to the data, information, or software a customer effectively consumes [22]. For example, Apple Music uses pay-per-use among other strategies to sell songs on its platform [16]. For Data-as-a-Service and Platform-as-a-Service models, scientists would have to pay every time they want access to data or a service. A prerequisite to cover the operating costs, however, is a critical number of transactions and thus a minimum number of users. However, as soon as this critical number is reached, the operating costs can be shared among the users, minimising the barrier for the individual scientist.

Subscriptions are fixed prices that customers have to pay at regular intervals for access to different kinds of services [15]. For example, the not-for-profit platform Taiwan eBook Supply Cooperative Limited (TEBSCO) offers e-books as part of a membership program. Participating users must pay a deposit as well as an annual membership fee to fund the provision of e-books. In return, members have access to a wide range of e-books as TEBSCO pools the purchasing power of its members to achieve cost benefits and enable sharing [23]. Moreover, according to the literature, subscriptions are users' most preferred option as it offers them unlimited access to different kinds of services [24]. However, membership fees may be a barrier for some users, which in turn might hinder the success of Open Science [25].

Based on the adapted version of Osterwalder et al. 's (2005) Business Model Canvas [3] for the selected ten Open Science IT Services overall, different private business models can be applied across the life cycle of Data-, Software-, and Platform-as-a-Service models. However, the analysed services are facing various challenges regarding the sustainability of their business models:

- When considering the target customer it is sometimes difficult to meet all funders' requirements and they might be ambivalent: indeed, there are differences in using Open Science/ FAIR-Data concepts between the scientific domains.
- Other challenges of Open Science IT Services are related to the value proposition. First, it is difficult for most services to communicate the value of their innovations to users, science, and society. Additionally, handling big amounts of data can be difficult and expensive.
- Considering the value creation, all Open Science IT Services depend on the infrastructure and support of their home institutions and there is a shortage of skilled staff and project time.

- The interviews showed that especially human resources are expensive. They make up about 70% of the costs for most of the interviewed services. To cover these costs a critical number of users is needed for every business model.
- Another challenge is the introduction of pricing mechanisms which is sometimes in conflict with constrictions imposed by the public funding sources which in all cases were the main funding source of the services. If the services home institution is publicly funded, creating a commercial income might not be admissible (see Interview I).

Summing up our findings and suggestions, since the number of users is usually low in the introduction phase, public support will be needed to sustain the operation of such services and to empower the establishment of Open Science. In the growth and maturity phase of the services, a combination of the described business models seems promising to provide all scientists open access to scientific data, community, and software.

3.3 Recommendations from international initiatives

The topic of sustainable business models in the context of research data and open science is one which is very relevant to the international research community, across many disciplines.

To stimulate and collect reflections around this topic, EOSC-Pillar participated in events where panels of representatives of inter-disciplinary communities would share their views and thoughts and interact with the audience.

Specifically, in this section, we present our experience with:

- the "EOSC-Pillar Business Model Workshop¹²", organised by the EOSC-Pillar and NI4OS INFRAEOSC-5b projects, in the form of a webinar on 1st July 2021: this was attended by 72 people, proceedings are available in the document accompanying milestone MS23¹³
- the workshop¹⁴ "National Policies relevant to EOSC deployment", attended by all the INFRAEOSC-5b regional projects (EOSC Synergy, Ni4OS, EOSC-Pillar, Expands, EOSC Nordic) together with FAIRsFAIR and EOSC Future, held in Strasbourg on 4th May 2022 (over 100 attendees - on-line and on-site, for further information please check the report¹⁵): one session was dedicated to "Funding policies".

Both events were conceived with a rather open-ended approach: neither aspired to provide an exhaustive overview of such a complex topic, nor to provide ready-to-use recipes.

On the other hand, the aim was to lay on the table as many hot points (successful or unsuccessful experiences, trend observations, caveats) as possible, providing food-for-thoughts to be expanded in other contexts.

¹² <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/events/webinar-eosc-pillar-business-model-workshop>

¹³ <https://repository.eosc-pillar.eu/index.php/s/ww9LdMP2PecfnYg>

¹⁴ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/news/national-policies-relevant-eosc-deployment-workshop-video-and-report>

¹⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6584214>

For the same reasons as above, it is difficult to extract "conclusions" and "recommendations", so the rest of this section will highlight a few interesting points which were brought up during the discussions and presented in the relevant reports mentioned above.

3.3.1 European context

European funding is (and has been over the last decades) a powerful instrument to innovate in the world of research. However, the project-funding approach brings at least two big issues: one is that research times are typically longer than the projects' (and funding programme's) timespan, and the other has to do with the long-term sustainability of valuable initiatives (which represents a problem per se and should, at the same time, be achieved in such a way as to not prevent new solutions from emerging).

For these reasons, there exists a shared feeling that, in the long term, research needs to progress towards more structured funding, which likely will move to the national level.

In this respect, it has been observed that the expenditure for research in Europe is often, with a few notable exceptions, below the 3% threshold¹⁶ which was established some 20 years ago by the European Council as the objective for research investment in Europe.

¹⁶ https://ec.europa.eu/invest-in-research/action/history_en.htm

Figure 10: Gross domestic expenditure on research and development (R&D) as a fraction of country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP): (online data code: TIPSST10) Source of data: Eurostat

There is thus a large potential for growth at national level. Some of the comments we received suggest that national funding may be most beneficial especially to "background" activities related to research, such as archiving and dataset publication.

It was also noted that it is important to keep the European and the national levels aligned, ensuring connection between the European interest and national strategies.

This implies not only the alignment of multi-annual roadmaps, but also an effort to adopt shared tools and methodologies. Connected to this last point, the example was made of unit cost calculation: besides representing an integral part of any business model, a sound methodology for unit cost calculation shared at the European level also helps to build confidence at the national level.

3.3.2 Building successful business models

It was widely recognized that a single or few business models could hardly be applicable throughout the research landscape. **Likely, each community should seek its own combination of business models, designed so as to rely on a diversified set of funding streams** in order to minimise the risk

of having gaps in the short term. In this respect, **in-kind contributions also represent a valuable source** which needs to be considered.

Identifying suitable and sustainable business models can be a daunting task in general, but especially for smaller or less structured research communities, which may risk lagging behind. The risk could be tackled already at the national level, for example by introducing some mechanism such that more structured research communities subsidise communities in the “long-tail” of science, especially for what concerns cross-border infrastructural needs.

3.3.3 Role of National Initiatives

Several comments suggest that the coordination role at the national level may be fulfilled by National Open Science Cloud Initiatives (NOSCI). Indeed, also owing to the efforts brought forward by EOSC-Pillar and the other INFRAEOSC-05b projects, the National Initiatives landscape has changed a lot over the last few years, with new Initiatives being constituted or reinforced, and a network of contacts being exploited.

NOSCI themselves need to plan for their own sustainability, which can be a challenging task, as it can prove difficult to convey to decision-makers the value of such Initiatives by demonstrating a direct relationship between effort spent and results obtained. For this reason, NOSCI are in some cases adopting very lightweight structures (based on MoUs, for example), largely relying on in-kind contributions.

4 Evolution of the EOSC landscape

The results detailed in the previous section can be seen as a snapshot taken at a specific moment of EOSC construction through different actions (surveys, interviews, workshops) undertaken during EOSC-Pillar lifetime. As the landscape is evolving very fast at European and National levels, it is important to document how EOSC construction has been progressing in the project partner countries during the project lifetime. Another important report, published at the very end of EOSC-Pillar, documents the main findings of the EOSC Financial Sustainability Task Force that we will summarise in this section.

4.1 Evolution of EOSC landscape in EOSC-Pillar partner countries

Key-structuring events have happened during the EOSC-Pillar lifetime that will have an impact on business models. The next subsections describe how the EOSC landscape has changed since the beginning of EOSC-Pillar in the countries participating in the project.

4.1.1 Belgium

Since the interview, Belnet, has reviewed its business model to meet future challenges. The federal government must have access to quality services that meet the most stringent security standards. But the price will always be a determining factor. Especially for the Research and Education (R&E) segment that uses Belnets services. The approach is based on obtaining a precise picture of their needs. This work was undertaken in community boards which began in 2020 and opened up to colleges in 2021. To sustain the access of the Internet exchange point to remain in Belgium and benefit society as a whole, a Belgian National Internet eXchange (BNIX)-specific strategy was developed to create a tailored and flexible approach to pricing, high value-added services, and a resale model for BNIX¹⁷.

As the mandated organisation, Belnet has deepened its connection with EOSC by taking on a leading role in the EOSC Focus project. EOSC Focus will support EOSC in its mission to make Open Science the new standard and achieve the goals outlined in the cooperation agreement between the European Union and EOSC. With its involvement in EOSC Focus, Belnet is concretizing and extending its commitment to Open Science by ensuring that it benefits the institutions connected to its network. Within the EOSC Focus project, Belnet will collaborate with eight other European members and contribute to improving the availability, accessibility and reuse of data. The project will make research results more accessible and facilitate the translation of scientific results into practical innovations for the benefit of the public.

Further, Belnet has strengthened its position by supporting Open Science and data infrastructure and services. DMPonline.be has been hosted by Belnet for several years, with users being able to authenticate easily and securely via the Belnet R&E Federation or via ORCID. Moreover, with the recent commissioning of a third data centre for the Belnet service infrastructure, very high availability is guaranteed. As of 2022, Belnet assumes full ownership of DMPonline.be, and continues

¹⁷ <https://www.belnet.be/sites/default/files/2022-12/RAEN2021.pdf>

the successful road of the DMPbelgium Consortium, which ensure the ability to continue to extend the usage of the DMPonline.be Belgium consortium to more users, without the need to join the consortium.

The co-involvement in the community-led RDM-tool supports the sustainable embedding of RDM-tools in the Belgium research landscape. With the management of DMPonline.be taken over by Belnet the business model has changed. The upscaling is viable as consortium members have become Belnet customers of DMPonline.be, and new customers are being added.

Belnet wants to ensure the continuity of the platform, making sure the latest available releases are being deployed, and new functionality can be added upon the need of the Belgian community of users while the entity of DMPonline.be stays Open Source. Besides the operational and technical aspects, Belnet will also be responsible for the further evolution of the platform, in function of the needs of the users. Lastly, Belnet shows intent to become active in the RDA Technical Advisory Board (TAB) by proposing a candidate for TAB membership. The results of the elections are not yet made public¹⁸.

4.1.2 France

After the interviews conducted by EOSC-Pillar, the French Ministry published the 5th edition (since 2008) of the National “[Research Infrastructure roadmap](#)”¹⁹. This document describes the research infrastructures labelled at a national level. Depending on their status, financial support is brought by the French state or by the research organisations in charge of the infrastructures.

In addition, the Ministry published the “[second French Plan for Open Science](#)”²⁰. The plan covers the period 2021-2024 and its goal is to generalise open science in France. The plan is structured in four paths that are 1) Generalising open access to publications, 2) Structuring, sharing and opening up research data, 3) Opening up and promoting source code produced by research and 4) Transforming practices to make open science the default principle.

Path 2 announces “We will create Recherche Data Gouv²¹ in order to involve all research fields in active practices of open data” . Officially launched on the 8th of July 2022, Recherche Data Gouv is “An ecosystem for sharing and opening research data”, offering a multidisciplinary data repository, a registry of data hosted in other repositories and a web portal. It is important to note that the Open Science Steering Committee chaired by the Ministry of Higher Education and Research's DGRI (Directorate-General for Research and Innovation) entrusted the development and management of

¹⁸ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/about-rda/organisational-bodies/rda-technical-advisory-board%C2%A0/tab-elections-2022-candidate-details>

¹⁹ <https://www.enseignementsup-recherche.gouv.fr/fr/la-feuille-de-route-nationale-des-infrastructures-de-recherche-2021-84056>

²⁰ <https://www.enseignementsup-recherche.gouv.fr/sites/default/files/2021-10/second-french-plan-for-open-science-13715.pdf>

²¹ <https://recherche.data.gouv.fr/en>

the Recherche Data Gouv platform to the National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment (INRAE which is a partner of the EOSC-Pillar project) .²²

Path 3 announces “Opening up and promoting source code produced by research”. The measure 7 aims at “Recognizing and supporting the dissemination under an open source licence of software produced by publicly funded research programmes” and the 9th focuses on “Promoting policies around free software”. It includes the support to Software Heritage and recommendation to use it for the archiving and referencing of source code.

Path 4 announces “Transforming practices to make open science the default principle”. One of the goals is to “make use of the research infrastructures which have signed up with the national roadmap²³ to transform practices and generalise open science”. The plan foresees to “implement the winning projects of the call for expressions of interest in Structuring Equipment for Research by the PIA which strengthens the development of infrastructures, platforms and services for thematic data”.

In summary, the “second French Plan for Open Science” guarantees support to the cited services and to the implementation of the actions. It has two practical consequences: the entities that provide the services will get direct financial support and it will facilitate the other sources of contributions to their budget.

4.1.3 Germany

Since the research and surveys done by EOSC-Pillar, the interest to provide reliable, interdisciplinary and FAIR data services has increased. Furthermore the leading German think tank for the digital transformation of science and information infrastructures, ‘Rat für Informations Infrastrukturen’²⁴ produced a comparative study in which over 40 data services including their respective business models were analysed and categorised²⁵.

A few notable examples of projects that deployed data infrastructures and services are mentioned here. NFDI has clearly moved into the position to support the EOSC development and co-develop the European data spaces. Driven by the incentives and ideas of EOSC, NFDI has started activities to organise the collection and development of a set of common services that have their counterpart in EOSC. In the Base4NFDI²⁶ cross cutting consortium, all existing NFDI consortia are represented and jointly work on establishing basic services. The uptake of services by Base4NFDI follows a three step process which means a technical selection followed by integration and operation steps. The integration step already requires a financial analysis on the feasibility and before operations a thorough analysis is performed, to assess whether sufficient evidence exists that the operational

²² From the general terms and conditions: <https://recherche.data.gouv.fr/en/page/general-terms-and-conditions>

²³ <https://www.enseignementsup-recherche.gouv.fr/sites/default/files/2022-03/feuille-de-route-nationale-des-infrastructures-de-recherche---2021-v2--17318.pdf>

²⁴ <http://rfii.de>

²⁵ <https://nbn-resolving.org/urn:nbn:de:101:1-2020052673>

²⁶ <https://base4nfdi.de/>

phase may be sustainably supported by commitments from participating or further institutions. Although this business model for the operation of services moves the responsibility to sustain the services towards the participating institutions the Base4NFDI consortium explicitly considers this an integral part of useful services operations. The consortium will align with the upcoming EOSC Core services which are being actively developed in the EOSC Future²⁷ project. The Core services are part of a procurement tender²⁸ which will fund the winning bid to run EOSC Core services for the 3 years starting from September 2023.

Another example of a cross cutting services infrastructure in Germany, the HIFIS project, delivered a set of production ready basic services, e.g data storage, AAI, software development, within the realm of the Helmholtz Association²⁹. The services continue to operate as part of the support infrastructure of several Helmholtz initiated scientific collaboration projects, some which specifically focus on data use and re-use e.g. the Helmholtz Meta-Data collaboration³⁰. Sustainability is guaranteed with direct funding by the partnering Helmholtz institutes. Awaiting further development of the NFDI initiated Base4NDFI, HIFIS is currently the only inter-disciplinary data services platform in Germany.

4.1.4 Italy

Since the research and surveys done by EOSC-Pillar, several Italian research centres and universities joined ICDI and ICDI started the process to establish itself as a legal entity: the vision aims to create a national coordination body that is representative of Italian infrastructures and interact with national and European institutions on their behalf³¹.

In June 2022, the Ministry of Universities and Research has published the “National Plan for Open Science” (PNSA, Piano Nazionale Scienza Aperta)³² the programmatic document through which the Italian government aims at contributing to the implementation of Open Science. The document is an essential part of the National Research Program (PNR), it is complementary to the PNIR, the National Plan for Research Infrastructures and it aims to create the conditions for the Italian full participation in European and international processes on Open Science. The National Research Program (PNR), covering the years 2021-2027, is a multi-year framework program that guides research policies in Italy under the coordination of the Ministry of Universities and Research and aims at strengthening the coordination of research policies at national and European level, with reference to the European and international dimension of research and considering regional initiatives and contributions.

²⁷ <https://eoscfuture.eu/>

²⁸ <https://etendering.ted.europa.eu/cft/cft-display.html?cftId=12087>

²⁹ <https://www.hifis.net/>

³⁰ <https://helmholtz-metadaten.de/en>

³¹ <https://www.icdi.it/en/about/members>

³² <https://www.mur.gov.it/it/atti-e-normativa/decreto-ministeriale-n-268-del-28-02-2022>

The PNSA states that the increasing volume of new data implies the development of an acquisition strategy of research data that must be “FAIR-by-design”. New technologies must be developed to facilitate the acquisition, automatised when possible, of FAIR datasets and their processing along with appropriate access and usage rules, in line with the ongoing developments of the EOSC. The PNSA is a policy document. ICDI has opened a dialogue with the Ministry for Research to develop a funding plan for implementation of the PNSA.

ICDI will also be the forum for the discussion of the implementation of the OS principles and integration into EOSC, the results of projects funded under the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR)³³, which started in September 2022 and are expected to be completed by December 2025. These are 5 National Centres for Supply Chain Research, 11 Territorial Innovation Ecosystems and 49 Research and Technology Innovation Infrastructures. In total, the investment amounts to more than EUR 4.3 billion.

4.2 EOSC Association Financial Sustainability Task Force Progress report

The objective of the Financial Sustainability Task Force is to produce a proposal for long term financial sustainability of the main building blocks of EOSC: EOSC-Core, EOSC-Exchange and the Federation of Data & Data Services as defined in the FAIR Lady report discussed previously.

In its first progress report [10] published in November 2022, the Task Force has scoped and defined the EOSC Exchange and Data Federation in the context of financial sustainability, identified barriers and boundary conditions, and performed initial development of financial scenarios for the EOSC Core, Exchange and Data Federation.

The Task Force’s proposed scenario for funding the **EOSC Core** is summarised as follows:

- The operational cost of the EOSC Core is to be funded jointly by the EC and the MS. This includes continuous incremental improvement aimed at operational relevance of current functionality, but not major investments in new functionality
- Countries associated with the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation should be able to contribute financially to the Core
- Financial contributions from third countries and others should be considered as additional sources of revenue (i.e. non-essential for operating the Core)
- In-kind contributions may be considered but do not confer the right to be exempted from the financial contribution.

Concerning **EOSC Exchange**, the task force identified three distinct types of service provisioning, each supported by a different financial model:

³³ <https://www.italiadomani.gov.it/content/sogei-ng/it/en/il-piano/missioni-pnrr/istruzione-e-ricerca.html>

- Centrally financed consumption of services - access to a certain amount of usage of selected services is made available to EOSC users, centrally financed by EOSC. This category is divided into two subsets:
 - A selective service portfolio of essential services (horizontal and thematic) which is 100% centrally funded
 - A small set of novel services which will receive temporary subsidies to initiate take-up in the research community
- Access to commercial services - procurement-compliant access to contracts with research-relevant commercial services
- Brokered not-for-profit services - community services brokered between the thousands of organisational participants in the EOSC with service transactions facilitated by the marketplace. This category constitutes the true marketplace of EOSC. It includes both horizontal and thematic services.

The Task Force has begun considering the possible exchange facilitation and remuneration mechanisms which may be available for the brokered services. Options include a voucher/token model, direct payment, and a subscription or freemium model. These require further research, including whether they will always require a central EOSC entity to broker financial transactions or whether money can flow directly from the institution to the service provider. The Task Force has identified **three possible scenarios for the future of the EOSC Exchange**:

- Establishing a pan-European single market for research services
- EOSC Exchange as a platform for window-shopping - an additional platform through which providers may display their services, involving no major change from today in how things are organised and funded
- Finding some middle ground between the first two options.

Finally, regarding **data federation**, the task force has made the following general observations:

- Data and services must go together in the design of EOSC, despite the fact that their financial scenarios are different
- Federating data implies interoperability between five levels of aggregation - institutional, national/regional, European, Thematic and international - which can cause duplication and confusion about allocation of responsibilities
- EOSC must consider existing data federations and repositories on different levels and make them discoverable on its portal
- EOSC is being created within a wider landscape including Common European Data Spaces, GAIA-X, the Global Open Science Cloud and other initiatives
- EOSC has an incentive to establish itself in a global context
- A full assessment of the financial needs of establishing and running the EOSC Data Federation requires consideration of costs at European level but also at local and national levels
- The EOSC Data Federation must be created using existing infrastructures and thematic ecosystems without duplicating efforts.

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Financial model for the data federation will depend on the agreed architecture that is still under definition. The aim of the task force is to provide by 2023 a proposal for long-term financial sustainability of the main building blocks of EOSC (EOSC Core, EOSC Exchange and the Federation of data & Data Services). It aims to draw on the outputs of other EOSC-relevant projects including EOSC-Pillar.

5 Conclusions

The surveys, interviews and workshops organised during the project lifetime have provided a wealth of information from users, service providers, National and International Initiatives.

The picture emerging from these exchanges with actors at EOSC-Pillar scale is a complex and fragmented landscape where there is no single answer to the question of the preferred EOSC business model.

At a national level, our analysis shows **many similarities between the five countries** involved in EOSC-Pillar (Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, Italy). In all of them, **public funding is the main source of revenue** for developing and operating services for Open Science. Public funding is also the primary source of revenue for similar initiatives in Australia, Canada, South Africa and even China. But **significant discrepancies can also be observed in the steps taken to develop a full business model**. Incentives to develop such business model include opening services outside the original community and at an international level and participation in a bid for procurement. Obstacles include the lack of motivation when the service scope is limited to the regional/national level and the lack of an agreed methodology to compute unit costs. A clear recommendation coming out of our exchanges with service providers is the need to develop a clear cost model to build trust with funders and users.

An **emerging concern expressed by the organisations interviewed is the environmental impact** of digital technologies. At the time of the interviews, the war in Ukraine had not started. This war has severely impacted the energy supply of European countries. As a consequence, **the cost of energy** has grown considerably, resulting in a very significant increase of the running costs for computing and storage resource providers in some countries (France). This new unexpected situation has not been taken into account in the business models that were produced before 2022 nor in the interviews. At the time of writing the deliverable, there are no short term perspectives for the end of the war and the restoration of normal economic relationships with Russia. As a consequence, there is no foreseeable end to the current uncertainties on the energy supply in Europe. As a consequence, the construction of EOSC must take into account the **need for optimising the energetic cost of the services** to be offered all along the data life cycle both for economic and environmental concerns.

Our exploration of business models for services coming out of scientific communities involved in EOSC-Pillar allowed us to identify several potential BM patterns for Open Science IT Services. Our conclusion is that public support will be needed to sustain the operation of such services and to empower the establishment of Open Science. In a later phase of maturity, a combination of advertising, commissioning, pay-per-use, subscription, and public funding seems promising for tackling the risk of funding gaps and for ensuring the sustainability of the Open Science IT services, but again a unique model is not foreseeable as legal frameworks are different in each European country and scientific communities have different cultures/practices. **Exploration of Innovative approaches should be encouraged, like for instance digital commons**. Digital commons are **non-rivalrous and non-exclusive resources defined by distributed and communal production, ownership**

and governance of informational capacities and technology. They intertwine collaborative governance and open data, open source as well as the principles of open standardization³⁴.

Representatives of international research communities shared their views and thoughts on business models during the workshops co-organized by EOSC-Pillar. They shared the long-term view of the **need to progress from project-based to more structured funding, most likely increasingly geared towards national funding:** as a consequence, they stressed the importance of keeping the European and the national levels aligned, in order to ensure the connection between the European interest and national strategies. This necessity to increase the level of national and European coordination, in particular on research infrastructures and e-infrastructures, is a concern also shared by the European Council and the e-IRG Reflection group [26].

Coordination among research communities should encourage the **adoption of shared tools and methodologies:** being part of an international effort (like the EOSC itself, or an established Research Infrastructure) can be a strong driver for standardization of tools and methods. Still on the topic of coordination, representatives of international research communities identified the potential **risk that smaller or less advanced communities may lag behind in the development of sustainable business models,** and suggested that more structured communities subsidise communities in the “long tail” of science.

Transnational service access also requires an European level organisation due to the complexity of the transactions. As discussed in the Strasbourg workshop in May 2022, access conditions to research data and resources differ between countries and infrastructure types [27]. Recommendations stemming from the workshop include increasing the uptake of implementation and fulfilment of FAIR principles, harmonising policies, licensing and procedures for storing and accessing data and resources at national and international level in order to build a sustainable model to fund access.

The workshops were also the opportunity to witness the emergence of National initiatives that could take over a coordinating role in the governance of Open Science development at the national level. In some cases, the issue of sustainability of National Initiatives is tackled by adopting very lightweight structures and largely relying on in-kind contributions.

Business models for EOSC are strongly correlated to its governance. Comparable Open Science initiatives outside Europe are structured through a charity in Australia and a non-profit organisation in Canada. The European e-infrastructures have similar legal status: EGI is for instance a Dutch foundation with membership fee to sit on EGI council. The services provided by EGI are provided by the different partners coordinated through the EGI.eu foundation. The costs to operate the services are covered by the partner and by EGI.eu through EU funding. The EU funding to e-infrastructures is under jeopardy as the new procurement policy introduced by the European Commission raises the risk that a significant amount of money migrates from e-Infrastructure to private companies. The outcome of the current calls for bids will be scrutinised by the EOSC ecosystem.

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https://www.diplomatie.gouv.fr/IMG/pdf/report_of_the_european_working_team_on_digital_commons_digital_assembly_june_2022_wnetherlands_cle843dbf.pdf

As stressed in the previous section, the EOSC ecosystem is evolving continuously and quickly both at national and European levels in a changing landscape. While National Open Science initiatives are growing in terms of structure and visibility, the results of the EOSC procurement tenders launched by the European Commission in December 2022 may either weaken or strengthen e-infrastructures in their contribution to provisioning EOSC Core Services.

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Appendix: additional questions from Business model canvas interviews)

Key Activities

- What are the most important activities for the operation of the service? (e.g., Software and hardware maintenance, IP-Management, Licensing)
- Can you describe your key activities?

Target users

- To whom do you offer your service?
- Which common needs, behaviors, and other characteristics define your user segments?

Value-Proposition

- Which benefits do you offer to the users?
- What does the users gain from using your services?
- Which user problems do you help to solve?

Impact

- What are the impacts of your services (economic, social, financial, environmental impact through improving energy efficiency, etc.) for your partners?
- Have you evaluated or/ and communicated the impacts of your services?
- Which strategies do you use to capture and communicate your impacts to users and partners?

User-Relationship

- How can potential target groups be won and retained?
- What kind of relationship do the different user segments (e.g. technical experts, beginners ...) expect from you (e.g. high-end technical features, tutorials ...)?
- Which ones have you already established?
- What do they look like, how are they maintained, and how (cost-) intensive are they?
- Could you identify the type of user agreements (legal vehicle, governance structure)?

Channels

- How are data & services delivered?

- How do you organize cross-organizational and cross-country service operations?
- Do you have any problems in expanding your service across organizations or countries?
- Do you have any restrictions or conditions imposed by your revenue stream regarding the channels? What kind of restrictions or conditions are they?

Key Partners

- Who are your key partners and key suppliers (currently)?
- What is their relationship with EOOSC?
- What is the motivation for each of the (possible) partnerships? (E.g. improving performance, saving effort and costs, reducing risks, access to resources, and performance).
- How are you building relationships with your (new) partners?
- Could you identify the type of partnership agreements (legal vehicle, governance structure)?

Key Resources

- Which key resources do you need for your service offering?
- Do you have any restrictions or conditions imposed by your revenue stream regarding the key resources? What kind of restrictions or conditions are they?

Cost structure

- What are the most important expenses without which your business model would not work?
- Which key resources are particularly cost-intensive?
- Which key activities are particularly cost-intensive?
- Do you use any specific cost evaluation methodology?

Revenue streams

- What are your funding streams?
- Can you identify the type of funding (investment, development, operational) and the scale of funding?
- What are the access conditions and pricing mechanism?
- Which percentage of total revenue do the respective revenue streams account for approximately?